

Shakespeare's Portrayal Of The Melancholy Jaques In *As You Like It*: A Literary Study

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Abstract

Fools and clowns in Shakespeare are multi-faced. Their presence in Shakespeare's comedies made a great contribution to the plays. The word 'Fool' was often used of a court-jester, quite an intelligent man who pretended to be half-witted or eccentric and under cover of his eccentricity shot the shafts of his acid wit on everybody, regardless of the rank or position of his victim ---- a role identical to that of Jaques in *As You Like It*. Melancholy is the permanent epithet for Jaques. But his melancholy deserves our censure rather than our admiration and our pity, because it leads to no useful action and because it is a self-indulgence to him. To Jaques, melancholy is a positive enjoyment and luxury. Whatever the cause of his melancholy, Jaques tells us that he is in love with it. It is true that Jaques' melancholy is a "pose" but it is wrong to hold that it is all a pose. It has a certain amount of reality in it. Jaques is a cynic to whom the world is no better than a great stage and all men and women merely players with their exits and entrances in an ephemeral pageant. It has been observed that Jaques' speech of the "Seven ages" must not be mistaken for a truthful description. Though the part by Jaques in the action seems to be quite insignificant his importance in the general scheme of *As You Like It* can hardly be over-estimated.

Keywords: Shakespeare, Jaques, comedy, fool and clown, seven ages.

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are

1. to plunge into the unfathomable depth of Shakespeare.
2. to take a minute look on the character of Jaques in the *As you Like It*,
3. to elicit information about his character traits as described in the drama.
4. to relate his character with the character of ordinary human beings of our global village.

Methodology

Love for literature is an evergreen technology to conserve environment. To build an understanding of various character traits of the melancholy Jaques in *Shakespeare's As you Like It* attempts have been made to collect available data both primary and secondary from various sources both living and non-living, online and offline like texts and various editions of *As you Like It*, research papers and journal articles published by the learned scholars on the topic of presentation and various websites. Paper has been prepared after careful analysis of those data accordingly.

Full Paper

Fools and clowns in Shakespeare are multi-faced. The clown or the court-jester was a stock character in Elizabethan plays – more commonly in the comedies, but also quite in their elements in tragedies too. In fact, the clown or the clownish character is invariably an essential figure in Shakespeare's tragedies, and Shakespeare has made various uses of this figure in accordance with the themes he is dramatizing. The Shakespearean Fool –

either in comedies or in tragedies – does not appear to be a stereotype or a stock-in-trade figure, even despite his motley in some plays, because he is absorbed within the structural frame as well as the inner frame of the total sensibility. Their presence in Shakespeare's comedies made a great contribution to the plays. They are defined as humorous characters with the main purpose of making people laugh. But they are not as simple as they seem. They are clever and observant and have many other purposes than just making people laugh. However, we have to pay attention on them carefully in order to realize the purpose and the meanings of their words. If we look at the role of a fool closely, we notice how clever they are. Those who cannot see the cleverness of the fools, are fools themselves. Fools in Shakespeare comedies behave as a mask for Shakespeare to criticize aspects of their own society, because only fools are allowed to speak out when others must be silent. They are allowed to tell the truth, and therefore fools became the most influential characters in the play. The word 'Fool' was often used of a court-jester, quite an intelligent man who pretended to be half-witted or eccentric and under cover of his eccentricity shot the shafts of his acid wit on everybody, regardless of the rank or position of his victim ---- a role identical to that of Jaques in *As You Like It*.

Jaques is one of the nobility that had followed the Duke in exile; but differing from other nobles who also had done so, in this that he had been actuated less by personal attachment to the good Duke, than by general hatred of a bad world, at

its worst about courts and cities. A youth ill-spent was what had brought him into this frame of mind. His travels had done nothing better for him than to Italianate him. When in the disgust that follows satiety he withdrew from the world and retired into himself, he came to be a hater and dispraiser of all mankind. Unlike the Duke Senior who sees good in everything Jaques, the man of chronic melancholy: can suck melancholy out of a song, as a weasel sucks eggs. ^(As You Like It; II.v.11-2)

Melancholy is the permanent epithet for Jaques. But his melancholy deserves our censure rather than our admiration and our pity, because it leads to no useful action and because it is a self-indulgence to him. To Jaques, melancholy is a positive enjoyment and luxury. This man of a melancholy disposition seeks to feed his melancholy rather than overcome it. No doubt he cultivates his mood of misery, but the feeling itself is real. He is a man of great intellectual and imaginative power and even great sensibilities, but he has made nothing of life. He has not lived his life well and wisely. And so the world has become for him 'a miserable world', ^(As You Like It; II.vii.13) fit to rail at. He speaks to Amiens, the personification of amiability that he finds as much pleasure in indulging in melancholy while listening to a song as a weasel finds when sucking the meat of an egg.

Jaques appears for the first time in the fifth scene of the Second Act of *As You Like It*. But we have already known much of him from the First Lord in the First Scene of the Second Act of the play. From what we have heard of him there we are in a position to assert that he is of a morose nature and sees evil in everything. His contemplation of the weeping deer shows that tears are a great luxury to him. He is perpetually finding fault with everything and everybody and does not spare even the innocent life of the Duke and his companions in the forest: Thus most invectively he pierceth through the body of country, city court, ^(As You Like It; II.ii.58-9) Here Jaques appears as a thorough pessimist believing in no man's honesty. He calls compliment is like th'encounter of two dog-apes. ^(As You Like It; II.v.23-4)

Melancholy is certainly the keynote to his character as Contentment is the leading feature of the banished Duke's character. Jaques loves melancholy better than laughing. He can suck melancholy out of a song, as a weasel sucks eggs. ^(As You Like It; II.v.11-2)

The only compliment he returns to Amiens is a parody of the worst possible kind. He is the only discord that jars with the woodland harmony of Arden.

Jaques has followed the Duke in exile, actuated by general hatred of a bad world at its worst about courts and cities. A youth ill-spent was

what had brought him into this frame of mind. When in the disgust that follows satiety he withdrew from the world and retired into himself his reflections on the world gave birth only to contempt for the world. Thus came Jaques to be a hater and despiser of all mankind; and this is pessimism or cynicism. Through the coloured glasses of this cynicism he saw nothing but evil everywhere; and this had made him melancholy; and this is where his character affords a complete antithesis to the banished Duke who finds “

tongues in trees, books in the running brooks, sermons in stones and good in everything. ^(As You Like It; II.i.16-7)

Unlike the Duke Senior, he finds evil in everything. He turns from the vanities of the court to seek comfort and consolation in nature and solitude. But he is of such a nature that he is doomed to be dissatisfied in whatever condition of life he may be. His character proves to us that a life of retirement and pastoral simplicity will not content all people alike and that contentment can only come from within. So even in the Forest of Arden Jaques is out of his sphere.

Jaques's melancholy however differs from the melancholy of all lovers of mankind who attempt to make mankind better than it is and fail. In his melancholy there was a want of this love. Hence he indulges in sickly sentimentality over the wounded deer, as if it better deserved that sympathy which he had withdrawn from undeserving mankind. This is the meaning of his lament over the wounded deer. The unreality of this feeling is shown when he is in such haste to dine off their venison that he is not prepared to wait for Adam to be brought into share it. Jaques's melancholy therefore, is not grave and earnest but sentimental, a self-indulgent humour

a petted foible of character, melancholy prepense and cultivated. ^(Powden 77)

Of course, his wild youth has something to do with it.

Whatever the cause of his melancholy, Jaques tells us that he is in love with it. From the Duke Senior's remarks on his past life we may perhaps gather that something akin to remorse for a not very creditable career has soured a temperament never very healthy or well-balanced. As to the character of his melancholy, it is neither that of the scholar which is the outcome of a feeling of rivalry among scholars; nor of the musician which arises out of fastidious tastes and subtle differences; nor of the courtier which comes of pride; nor of the soldier which is another name for ambition; nor of the lawyer which it is politic for him to assume; nor of the lady which arises out of pride, rivalry etc. This is the indirect explanation of the nature of his melancholy. But Jaques does not stop there. He tells

us what melancholy is like. It is a melancholy of mine own, compounded of many samples, extracted from many objects; and indeed the Sunday contemplation of my travels, which by often rumination and wraps me in a most humourous sadness. From this it appears that the melancholy of Jaques is a self-indulgent humour, a foible of character which he cultivates because under its grab his ill humour may have free play. For if not actively malignant, his melancholy betrays itself chiefly in girdling at the order of things in general. The sufferings of the wounded deer are made the text for a homily on the heartlessness of mankind be they of whatever station or manner or life. Out of a song, however merry, he

can suck
melancholy.....as a weasel sucks egg.^(As You Like It; II.v.11-2)

He envies the fool's license of speech and would himself have life privilege to "blow on" whom he pleases. Meeting Orlando, he assumes his self-conferred role of general censor, but retires discomfited. Though offering to give away Audrey in marriage to Touchstone, he takes the opportunity of lecturing them on the sin meditated in an irregular ceremony. It is true that Jaques' melancholy is a "pose" but it is wrong to hold that it is all a pose. It has a certain amount of reality in it. As Verity justly comments:

His (Jaques') melancholy is in part that disgust with self and the world which is the nemesis of choosing the wrong path.⁽¹⁵²⁾

So his melancholy is not all a sham and a pretense. The feeling, though consciously indulged is real.

Jaques is a cynic to whom the world is no better than a great stage and all men and women merely players with their exits and entrances in an ephemeral pageant. Man's life is only a comedy-play. Men and women strut and fret their hour upon the stage and then are heard no more. Each one has seven contemptible parts of play.

The First Act of the human drama reveals the infant mewling and puking in the nurse's arms.^(As You Like It; II.vii.144)

The Second Act finds the infant the whining school boy;^(As You Like It; II.vii.145) with his satchel and shining morning face, creeping like snail unwillingly to school.^(As You Like It; II.vii.146-7)

In the Third Act the school boy appears as the lover Sighing like furnace;^(As You Like It; II.vii.148) and composing tragic verses to the eye of his beloved.

In the Fourth Act the lover is transformed into the soldier; full of strange oaths, and bearded like the pard, quick in quarrel,^(As You Like It; II.vii.151)

and ever ready to be in the thickest of the fight, even at the deadly cannon's threat in order to seek the bubble reputation.^(As You Like It; II.vii.152)

In the Fifth Act the soldier is succeeded by the portly judge, fond of good living, with eyes severe and beard of formal cut.^(As You Like It; II.vii.155)

His fair round belly is lived with good capon (accepted as bride),^(As You Like It; II.vii.154) his talk 'full of wise saws and modern instances' .^(As You Like It; II.vii.156)

The Sixth Act transforms the Justice of the Peace into the lean and slipper'd pantaloon,^(As You Like It; II.vii.158)

his breeches much too big for his shrunk shank;^(As You Like It; II.vii.161)

his big manly voice changed into childish treble;^(As You Like It; II.vii.162)

his eyes wearing spectacles; his side dangling a pouch.

The Seventh act and Last Act of this strange eventful drama shows the man of age lapsing back into

second childishness,^(As You Like It; II.vii.165)

and mere oblivion,

sans teeth, sans eyes, sans taste, sans everything.^(As You Like It; II.vii.166)

It has been observed that Jaques' speech of the "Seven ages" must not be mistaken for a truthful description. It is a caricature of the life of man, as seen by his distorted vision, and as meant to illustrate his constant theme that man's life is a farce, not worth the living and acting. Jaques is a man of lively imagination and artistic temperament. The seven pictures are drawn with extraordinary clearness and vivid force, and their subjects appeal to universal experience. Jaques indeed is a maker of fine sentiments, a dresser forth in sweet language of the ordinary common-places or the common-place mishaps of life. Jaques is extremely sensitive and as is usual with morbid sensitive temperaments, cultivates his mood of misery. But the feeling itself, though consciously indulged, is real. It is in part that disgust with self and the world which is bound to result from his wild youth.

Beside Touchstone, Jaques is the figure that serves chiefly to blend and harmonise the masses of light and shade of the court and country life of which the play consists on which its great effectiveness depends. Perhaps Shakespeare introduced Jaques as an extra precaution against the play becoming pastoral convention. For Jaques is an extreme anti-romantic. He loves the life of the greenwood for what it is and not for its fancied prettiness. If the Duke finds the sweet and bracing influences of Nature in forest, Jaques sees the struggle of life repeating itself in folly, selfishness and misery, Jaques is a philosopher whose wit provides a commentary on life peculiarly derived

from his own temperament, while Touchstone has no particular self to express, but merely turns on the wit of professional clown to extract humour from the situation in which he finds himself. Jaques' removal from the plot of the comedy would entirely alter the composition of the whole. He is a foil to the Duke in his melancholy, to the lovers in his philosophy and to Touchstone in his humour.

Jaques is a bundle of inconsistencies, a mixture of witty sensibility and merry sadness, a child of folly and a professor of wisdom. At one moment he loves his melancholy better than laughing, at another he laughs 'sans intermission an hour by his dial',^(As You Like It; II.vii.32-3) at one time he seeks society, at another solitude. If one reason of Jaques's failure in life is the squanderings in his wild youth; another is his sensibilities. He is perpetually finding fault, railing on Lady Fortune, censuring all mankind, aiming his sarcasms at persons of all conditions. Even the innocent life of the Duke and his companions in the forest does not escape his satire. He is a thorough pessimist, believing in no man's honesty. In his opinion, all are either fools or knaves. The world has become for him a miserable world, but fit to rail at and discover fresh matter of disgust in. He ridicules what average humanity holds most precious. Love to him is the worst fault, and complement the 'encounter of two dog-apes',^(As You Like It; II.v.23-4) The high-born --- 'the first-born of Egypt',^(As You Like It; II.v.58) --- and those who have succeeded in this world --- 'fat and greasy citizens',^(As You Like It; II.i.55) --- are specially the marks of his satire. In his comparison of the world with a stage he seizes upon what is ridiculous to the exclusion of what is noble or blessed. He envies the state of the professed fool simply because it brings with it the privilege to 'blow on' whom he pleases.

Thus, the somber reflection of Jaques serves to heighten the effect of the gaiety of the other persons. His character is true to life in the Aristotelean sense, and has a strong sense of verisimilitude. Furthermore, while Jonson's characters are narrow, flat and monolithic in terms of capturing just one trait, Shakespeare's characters are complex, flexible, capable of accommodating changeability and psychologically deep. Not a single character of Jonson can match the depth and philosophical profundity of Jaques in *As You Like It*. Though the part by Jaques in the action seems to be quite insignificant his importance in the general scheme of *As You Like It* can hardly be over-estimated. There is no iota of doubt that he is of all the characters, the gravest, the most intellectual --- in a word, the strongest; and it is through him that the comedy approaches Shakespeare's later and more serious work.

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